

Fig 1. Diaphragm of camel showing Os diaphragmaticum (P), Oesophagus (O), Posterior venacava (V) and Tendinous part (T)

Fig 2. Radiograph of diaphragm of camel showing Os diaphragmaticum (P) and groove (G) on its ventral border

Fig 3. Photograph of Os diaphragmaticum (P) separated from the diaphragm of camel with groove (G) on the ventral border

Summary

The diaphragm of camel consisted of a costal, sterna (muscular) and lumbar parts (tendinous

part). In camel lumbar (tendinous part) was larger than the muscular part. *Os diaphragmaticum* (*Os phrenic*) was placed between oesophagus and *posterior vena cava*. It was triangular in shape and measured 3.7 cm in length and 2.5 cm in width. It consisted of two surfaces *i.e.*, cranial and caudal and three borders. The ventral border showed a groove for the passage of *caudal vena cava*.

References

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Anatomy of Diaphragm and *Os Diaphragmaticum* in Camel

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The diaphragm and *Os diaphragmaticum* have been studied in camel by Grossman (1960) Nagpal *et al.* (1985) and Etemadi (1966). But information on its anatomical relations and functional importance is scarce. Hence, the present study was undertaken to provide comprehensive information on the above.

Material and Methods

The study was conducted on the diaphragms of two adult camels which were brought to the Department of Pathology for postmortem examination. Immediately after the death the thoracic cavity was dissected through an incision at the level of sternum and by removing lateral thoracic wall. The lungs were pulled laterally to approach the thoracic surface of the diaphragm. On opening the abdominal cavity, the comparative relationship of the liver and reticulum of stomach to the diaphragm especially to the *os diaphragmaticum* was studied. Then diaphragm was dissected out and cleaned off the attached fat. After recording the gross observations radiographs were taken at 55 KV and 16 mAs (milli amperes per second).

Results and Discussion

The diaphragm of the camel consisted of a muscular part which was divided into costal and sternal parts and a lumbar part composed of two crura and a tendinous centre. The costal part was attached to the costal cartilages of the seventh, eighth and ninth ribs, whereas, sterna part was attached to the caudal part of the sternum. The lumbar part had right and left crus. The left crus

was smaller and attached to the first and second lumbar vertebrae. Its thoracic surface was associated with lungs, whereas, abdominal surface was in contact with the liver and the reticulum of the stomach. The tendinous surface area of the diaphragm in the camel was relatively larger than the muscular portion.

In the present study radiographs were also taken from isolated diaphragms. Radiographic study revealed that an ossified bone placed between *hiatus oesophagus* and *foramen vena cava*. In this animal the bone appeared roughly quadrilateral. In the other animal, the bone was triangular in shape and consisted of two surfaces, three borders and three angles. The thoracic (cranial) and abdominal (caudal) surfaces were convex and attached to the tendinous centre. Its base was directed towards the right side and its apex towards the left. The average length and width of the bone was 3.7 cm 2.5 cm respectively. The bone was covered completely by tendinous fibres at the centre of the diaphragm in front of the crura. The tendinous and muscular fibres were attached to it. The ventral border of the bone was grooved for the *caudal vena cava*. The left lateral border showed a rough edge for tendinous attachment. The right lateral border was thick and convex. The angles were dorsal, left ventral and right ventral. The dorsal and left ventral angles were almost round. The right ventral angle was bifid and plate like. This supported and gave attachment to the *caudal vena cava*. This bone keeps the *vena cava* open and protected it against compression during swallowing.

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